

THE ROLE OF WORKING TOOLS IN THE STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE PRIMITIVE SOCIETY IN CENTRAL ASIA

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the main factor in the emergence of the longest-lasting primitive society in human history is the appearance of working tools, the gradual improvement of working tools, the stone industry, the features of stone processing and archaeological research on stone tools were analyzed. The article also analyzed the scientific archeological research conducted on the stone tools of the primitive period in Central Asia.

KEYWORDS: *Primitive period, working tools, primitive stone working tools, stone industry, bone working tools, primitive sites, Ashel and Muste stone tools, working tools of Kaltaminor culture.*

INTRODUCTION

The period from the appearance of primitive people to the emergence of the state is the period of primitive communities. Collective work and consumption is a characteristic of primitive society. Primitive man with the simplest tools of labor could not fight alone against the forces of nature and wild animals. That is why primitive people worked collectively and shared the product of their labor equally. [3, pp. 7-9]

The oldest and longest period of human history is the primitive period, and through scientific data, especially archeology, we can get a certain idea about the life, lifestyle and customs of early humanity.

The labor process, which played an important role in the separation of the oldest people from the natural world, and caused the creation of early material culture samples. [8, pp. 23-25] By making the simplest weapons, man created himself and established a boundary between the animal world and man, which was the first step in the separation of man from the natural world.

METHODS

A characteristic feature of primitive society is the extremely low level of development of production forces and the use of stone in the development of labor tools during the main stages of development of this period. It was very difficult to make simple weapons from stone, and it took many millennia to improve its production. In addition, in the early stages of development, labor productivity was at a low level, and people still had a low level of life and production experience. [7, pp. 37-38] However, over the centuries, the improvement of labor tools continued.

No matter how simple the tools of labor created by primitive people, the economy is a very rich combination of various elements of the social foundation and ideology. This culture gradually grew from simple to complex forms. This primitive culture is a necessary condition for the further development of personality, and has become the basis of its further development as a higher form of being. Many of the achievements of primitive people have retained their importance in the treasury of modern culture. In the past, the individuality has traveled the path of the entire primitive period, and tribes and peoples have independently traveled through this period to a certain extent, created their own culture and preserved the culture in general. [10, pp. 125-126] In order to fully and adequately imagine the development of primitive culture, it is not appropriate to be limited to the existing information about different tribes and peoples, it is necessary to make a scientific analogy with the information about different peoples in different countries of the world.

The emergence and development of man is a unique and unrepeatable phenomenon in the history of the organic world, which is associated with extremely

favorable conditions. The place where this great event took place covers a very large area, including the southern part of Asia, southern Europe and a large part of Africa.

Archaeologist S.P. Tolstov discovered the Kaltaminor culture in Khorezm, in Central Asia. Several locations of this culture exist in Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan. At one of the sites in Uzbekistan, a settlement was found, built on land with an area of about 320 m, which is very large for the Neolithic, and in the center of it there are remnants of cooking fires, and in the center there are the remains of an oven that served for religious worship, possibly unrelated to the environment. [13, pp. 161-165]

RESULTS

Archaeological data is important in studying the history of primitive society. The emergence of man is related to tools. Of course, this process should be noted separately, regardless of the source of science, in any conditions, they remain relative. For example, the tools of the Paleolithic period cannot be considered completely studied. It is possible to have a realistic idea of the life and history of a primitive society only thanks to the comprehensive study of all kinds of sources. In this regard, the method of comparative comparison of ethnographic sources can give important results. The first material that served the earliest ancestors of man for weapons and armor was stone, specifically flint, and related material rocks, especially flint. Flint is very common in all parts of the globe, and this mineral has a very important property (dissolving into hard and soft materials, giving sharp cutting edges). [11, pp. 78-81] All this shows that flint has played an important role in human life. Archeological excavations of the Stone Age were first carried out in France. Later, such excavations were carried out in other parts of the world. It testifies to the continuous growth of the collected materials and techniques and allows identifying several stages.

Most scientists believe that man appeared on earth with artificially prepared tools of labor. The continuous use of labor tools by primitive people in life gradually activated the use of natural resources. The scope of work is always expanding. People unite for using natural resources in life, collective hunting is formed. The process of

development of working tools has a great impact on social life, and social life is gradually becoming more complicated. [6, pp. 31-33]

These successive stages are determined by specific human activities found in different parts of the globe, and in science, man and the tools he produced call the traces left culture. These cultures are named after the places where they were found, and they are the largest centers of this culture. [2, pp. 25-31]

The simplest early stage of culture is the Acheulean culture. (Named after the town of Saint-Ashel in northern France). The main type of weapons of this era culture is a rather large almond-shaped piece of stone with a length of 10 cm to 20 cm and a weight of 500 g to 1 kg. This weapon is called "hand chopper" or "hand axe". Because these weapons were easy to hold, their thick back had a smooth part called "heel". Ashel chisel served as a striking and cutting, carving and at the same time throwing weapon in almost all works. [5, pp. 25-38]

The character of the weapon of this culture is no different from that of the Shel period, but it is slightly smaller, more straight in shape, and much better made in the so-called "retouch" method. Stone tools of no particular type have been found at Ashel sites, as at Shel sites. In addition to distinguishing weapons in Ashel addresses from Shel addresses, Yana is also distinguished by other signs indicating a person's life and activities. Many bones of wild animals such as mammoth, rhinoceros, as well as traces of fire have been preserved.

Deer Koba cave, discovered by S.N.Zamyatnin in 1925-28 and V.A.Gorodsov in 1936-37, near Ilesk station, 4.3 km southwest of Kuba and Krosnodar, is considered one of the great monuments of Muste culture. [4, pp. 294-299]

Such monuments of Muste culture were also found in Uzbekistan. Surkhandarya. Teshiktash cave in Boysun Mountain of the region is one of them. [2, pp. 37-52]

At the beginning of the Muste period, the technique is characterized by a significant increase. The spear, typical of the previous stages, is rare in this period, its size is much larger, and its structure is much rougher. Korakcha is also considered one of the important tools of Muste culture.

At this stage, sharp-edged weapons were made from bone, a new material. Muste sites are usually found in large numbers of large animals, often mammoth, then rhinoceros, cave bear, wild horse, reindeer and others.

As a result of continuous improvement of working tools during the stages of transition from the first Paleolithic to the last Paleolithic, the modern type of man was formed. Human associations formed during the Early Paleolithic period formed a strong community that developed to a certain extent by the Late Paleolithic period. In this way, collective labor created conditions for collective living. Working experiences increased. The technology of making weapons was improving. This process was passed down from generation to generation. The emergence of the primitive collective had a great impact on the development of production forces. The development of production forces, first, led to an increase in the technology of making weapons from stone. [14, pp. 103-104] Now, people started to use the technology of extracting thin long sheets from stone core instead of shapeless rough pieces of stone. Compact, sharp, high-performance weapons began to be produced thanks to the technique of making small cuts on both sides of such sharp-edged sheets. This method also made it possible to save raw materials. Due to the introduction of new technology, various special weapons were made that perform different tasks. For example, special weapons such as scrapers, chisels, perforators, and knives were produced, the differentiation of production increased, the possibility of making labor tools increased, and this process gradually accelerated.

In the production of late Paleolithic weapons, handles were attached to some of them, and weapons with handles were produced. This was considered an important stage of social production. In addition to stone, weapons were made from animal bones and horns. [11, pp. 78-81] For example, the production of weapons such as needles, plow teeth, spear blades and fishing rods was started. In addition, weapons that could be placed on a base plate and fired at a distance began to be developed. These weapons doubled the range of the javelin. Fishing rods were made from animal bones. Therefore, the appearance of such equipment and weapons created conditions for the increase of

hunting products and for the members of the community to have enough food. Because of the invention of such weapons, the hunting industry developed more and more. According to the results of archaeological excavations, people now have the opportunity to hunt large herds of animals. For example, about 800-1000 mammoth bone remains were found in Prjedmoste, Czechoslovakia, a Late Paleolithic site, along with more than 40,000 weapons. 10,000 horse bones were found in France's Solutry area, and 1000 bison bones were found in Amrosievka area in Ukraine. Many bones of large animals such as horses, bulls, and deer were found in Samarkand area with various stone tools. Now, hunting has provided the people with a certain level of self-sufficient food.

DISCUSSION

By the end of the Paleolithic period, people moved to use not only caves, but also artificially built huts and basement huts. True, as mentioned above, the construction of living huts is known from the Middle Paleolithic muster period. However, the construction of dwellings for living becomes widespread in the Late Paleolithic period. The area occupied by some dugout dwellings reached 200 m². The lower walls of some of them consist of stone pillars, they are built in the form of cones, and the roofs are covered with branches and animal skins. For example, the length of the hut found in the Kostenko area near Voronezh was 35 m, and the width was 15-16 m. There are nine hearths around the central pillar. During this period, in addition to such large huts, "villages" consisting of several smaller huts are also formed. During the Late Paleolithic period, the cold climate of the Vomer Ice Age enters. This phenomenon affects the evolution of human clothing. Compared to the abundance of found bone needles, animal skins were widely used for not only covering the upper part of houses, but also for sewing and dressing clothes. In the last Paleolithic period, in order to illuminate the huts at night, the method of using animal bones, pouring animal fat into the stone, and installing a wick to provide light, in short, a wick lamp of its time appeared. The progressive development of productive forces leads to the improvement of productive forces and relations. [1, pp. 17-24]

CONCLUSION

No matter how simple the ancient culture created by them is, it consists of various elements of technology, social foundation and ideology. This culture has grown steadily, gradually moving from the simple to the higher and more complex forms. This primitive culture is a necessary condition for the further development of civilization, and became the basis of the next method in its highest form.

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